

Metanilic acid is found inactive as a dehydrating catalyst. This retarding action of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group was also observed by Dole and Keskar (*loc. cit.*).

Esters of Sulphonic Acids.—The esters of sulphonic acids are found to be active, but unlike the free sulphonic acids, they are less active at 250° . When the temperature of dehydration is increased to 280° , the reaction becomes rapid. The reactivity of the esters may be due to their hydrolysis into free sulphonic acids. It may also be assumed that the esters react by way of rupture of the alkyl-oxygen linkage (Ferns and Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 273; Philips, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 44). When the reactivity of the esters is compared with the corresponding free acids, it is observed that (i) esters are less active than free acids, (ii) in the case of esters, hydrolytic reaction is less, and (iii) comparatively pale coloured dehydrated products are obtained. Moreover, the activities of methyl and ethyl esters are similar.

From the above observations, it is probable that only a part of the ester breaks up into free acid, which is supposed to be responsible for the catalytic reaction.

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DEHYDRATION OF CASTOR OIL BY PHENOL-SUBSTITUTED SULPHONIC ACIDS AND THEIR POTASSIUM SALTS

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Among several phenol-substituted sulphonic acids and their salts, employed as dehydrating catalysts in dehydration of castor oil, *p*-phenol-, *m*-cresol- and resorcinol-sulphonic acids have been found to be active at 250° ; potassium salts of *p*-phenol- and *m*-cresol-sulphonic acids are active both under atmospheric pressure and under reduced pressure; potassium guaiacol-sulphonate is found to be active under atmospheric pressure. Phosphoric acid, sodium dihydrogen phosphate and ammonium dihydrogen phosphate have also been studied as catalysts; among the three, phosphoric acid is found to be a good catalyst, and is reactive at 280° and affords exceptionally pale coloured dehydrated product with low acid value. The other two are found to be inactive.

The use of different naphthol-sulphonic acids as catalysts for dehydration of castor oil was reported by Walton, Coffey and Knapp (*Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 6557). They claimed that 2-naphthol-6-sulphonic acid afforded 100% dehydration of the oil at 260° in one hour with less amount of decomposition of the oil. Dole and Keskar (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 38A, 135) also found phenol-sulphonic acid to be a useful dehydrating catalyst and observed that the introduction of $-\text{OH}$ group in the benzenesulphonic acid mitigated the tendency of decomposition of the oil without affecting the dehydrating capacity of the catalyst. As a consequence, phenol-sulphonic acid gave paler products than benzenesulphonic acid. Potassium salt of phenol-sulphonic acid was also studied and reported by them to be a good dehydrating catalyst.

In view of the above encouraging results, the use of some more phenol-substituted sulphonic acids as catalysts has been studied in the present investigation.

Phenol-substituted free sulphonic acids were quite active at 250°. The dehydration was rapid at 270° in the case of the potassium salts of phenol-sulphonic acids. The dehydration was therefore carried out at 250° in the former case and at 270° in the latter. When *m*-cresol-sulphonic acid, *p*-phenol-sulphonic acid, salts of *p*-phenol-sulphonic, *m*-cresol-sulphonic and guaiacol-sulphonic acids were used as catalysts, the period of dehydration was one hour. In the remaining catalysts, the period of dehydration was 50 minutes.

It was observed that phosphoric acid was less active at 250°, but its activity increased when dehydrated at 280°. The acid salts of phosphoric acid, viz., sodium dihydrogen phosphate and ammonium dihydrogen phosphate, were found to be inactive even when 5.0% of each was employed for dehydration.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dehydration reaction was carried out under atmospheric pressure (near about 713 mm of mercury) and under vacuum (20 mm of mercury). The experimental and analytical procedures adopted in this investigation are the same as described before (Dole and Keskar, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

Values of samples dehydrated with phenol-substituted sulphonic acids and their potassium salts as catalysts.

No. Catalyst	Pressure.	Conc. of catalyst.	I. V.	H. V.	A. V.	M. W.	R. I.	Colour, B. R. Y.
1. Resorcinol-sulphonic acid	713 mm	0.3%	138.3	49.6	4.3	976.3	1.4780	I 14' II
Do	20	0.3	155.7		2.0	925.5	1.4790	0 10 18
2. <i>m</i> -Cresol-sulphonic acid	713	0.4	142.7	44.1	4.0	1101	1.4770	
Do	20	0.4	155.1	29.7	1.8	913.0	1.4795	
3. 2-Naphthol-1-sulphonic acid	713	0.3	104.1	125.9	5.1	...	...	
4. 2:4-Dinitro-1-naphthol-7-sulphonic acid	713	0.1	107.0	105.5	4.2	982.8	1.4735	
5. <i>p</i> -Phenol-sulphonic acid	713	0.3	131.3	55.7	6.0	967.9	1.4765	
6. K <i>p</i> -phenol-sulphonate	713	3.0	150.5	29.7	6.8	969.0	1.4775	
Do	20	3.0	156.4	16.5	8.7	879.0	1.4780	
7. K <i>m</i> -cresol-sulphonate	713	2.0	148.8	44.3	5.0	1001	1.4780	
Do	20	2.0	164.1	21.2	3.1	944.0	1.4795	
8. K guaiacol-sulphonate	713	2.0	147.5	35.2	3.6	1001	1.4800	1.0 2.3 12
Do	20	2.0	90.0	154.0	...	...	...	

I. V. : Iodine value by Wübborn method at room temperature (27°-28°).

H. V. = hydroxyl value; A. V. = acid value; M. W. = Molecular weight by cryoscopic method using benzene, special for molecular weights.

R. I. = Refractive index by Abbe's refractometer at 40°.

Colour : By Lovibond tintometer using 10 mm. cell; B-Blue; R-Red; Y-yellow.

TABLE II

Rate of dehydration of castor oil.

No.	Catalyst.	Conc. of catalyst.	I. V. of samples drawn at intervals (in mins.) of							
			10.	15.	20.	30.	40.	45.	50.	60.
1.	Resorcinol-sulphonic acid.	0.3%	130.7	...	136.2	138.0	138.4	...	138.3	...
2.	<i>m</i> -Cresol-sulphonic acid	0.4	136.1	...	140.3	141.6	142.3,	...	142.5	142.7
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenol-sulphonic acid	0.1	97.1	...	100.4	103.0	104.0	...	107.0	...
4.	K <i>m</i> -cresol-sulphonate	2.0	...	132.1	...	141.4	...	148.6	...	148.8
5.	K guaiacol-sulphonate	2.0	122.4	...	136.1	143.2	146.9	...	147.1	147.5

TABLE III

Physical and chemical characteristics of the dehydrated castor oil samples.

Conc of phosphoric acid = 0.3%.

Temp. of dehydration = 280° ± 5°.

Time of dehydration = 60 minutes.

	At 713 mm.	At 20 mm.		At 713 mm.	At 20 mm.
I. V. (Woburn)	151.5	147.8	Ref. index at 40°	1.4800	1.4815
Hydroxyl value	23.5	23.7	M. W.	877.6	899.1
Acid value	11.2	6.4	Colour :	B 0.0	0.0
Sapon. value	194.7	182.1		R 1.1	0.4
				Y 10.0	0.8

DISCUSSION

Phenol-substituted sulphonic acids are active dehydrating catalysts. They furnish paler products than benzenesulphonic acid.

Due to the high temperature of the dehydration reaction the decomposition of the oil is rapid. The decomposition products produced at the temperature of reaction may be oxidised, and may thus cause the dark colour of dehydrated samples. In the case of phenol-substituted sulphonic acids, the oxidation of the decomposition products is checked to a great extent, due evidently to the antioxidant property of phenols.

It is observed that dehydrated castor oil is sensitive to antioxidants (Ijak, *Chem. Paint*, 1951, 14, 188). Thus, the improvement in the colour of the dehydrated products, when hydroxy-substituted aromatic sulphonic acids are used as catalysts, may be due to their inhibiting influence on this oxidation of the oil and the decomposition products.

The potassium salts of phenolic sulphonic acids are active due to their slightly acidic character of the salts. Thus, potassium salts of *m*-cresol-sulphonic and *p*-phenol-sulpho-

nic acids are active both under atmospheric and reduced pressures. Potassium guaiacol-sulphonate is, however, found to be active only under atmospheric pressure.

Phosphoric acid is also found to be an active dehydrating catalyst. It gives paler products than benzenesulphonic acid. Under reduced pressure, the dehydrated sample has an exceptionally pale colour and low acid number. In this case also it may be surmised that, like phenol-substituted sulphonic acids, the oxidation of the decomposition products is retarded to a great extent, and the antioxidant property of phosphoric acid (Bailey, "The Retardation of Chemical Reactions", 1937, Edward Arnold and Co. London, p. 118) may be the cause for this improvement in colour.

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